

CHILD LABOURS IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT :

The problem of child labour has been more serious in developing countries. Due poverty, hunger, illiteracy, ignorance, traditional thinking and lack of proper implementation of child labour laws in our country, the problem of child labour is still persist in our society. The children of age below 14 years have working in various fields and in very hazardous conditions. The number of child labour has been increasing in our country and the number of child labour is more in our country as compared to any other country in the world. Many provisions are provided in our constitution and in laws to control child labour but socio-economic conditions prevalent in the country do not force children to get compulsory education and to enjoy right to education. The attempt has been made in this paper to provide brief account of child labour laws in our country, reasons for child labour and suggestions to control child labour.

Keywords: *Child Labour, Causes effects and Law.*

Introduction:

In developing countries it is impossible to control child labour as children have been considered as helping hand to feed their families, to support their families and to feed themselves. Due to poverty, illiteracy and unemployment parents are unable to bear the burden of feeding their children and to run their families. So, poor parents send their children for work in inhuman conditions at lower wages. The child labour lead to underdevelopment, incomplete mental and physical development, which in turn results in retarded growth of children. Due to lack of proper implementation of child labour laws, improper implementation of child welfare plans and improper checks by department of women and child welfare, the problem of child labour has been still persisting in our society in urban as well as in rural areas. Children in our country work as rag pickers, dish washers in dabhas, as labourers in small factories, as domestic helpers in big cities. India has largest number of children employed than any other country in the world. Around 90 million out of 179 million children in the age group of 6-14 year do not go to school and are engaged in some occupation or other so around 50 percent of children of our country are involved in child labour. A large numbers of children are engaged in cottage industries: carpet, matches, firecrackers, bidis, brassware, diamond, glass, and hosiery, hand loomed cloth, leather goods, plastic, bangles, sporting goods, at shops as helpers.

Objectives:

1. To Study the meaning of child Labour.
2. To Study the Effects of child labour
3. To Study the Governments Polices to prevent child Labour System.

Research Methodology:

For this research paper the secondary data is collected. The data have collected from various sources such as reference book, newspapers and websites etc.

What is Child Labour

Child labour typically means the employment of children in any manual work with or without payment. Child labour is not only limited to India, it happens to be a global phenomenon.

As far as India is concerned, the issue is a vicious one as children in India have historically been helping parents at their farms and other primitive activities. Another concept that needs explanation is the concept of bonded labour which is one of the most common forms of exploitation. Bonded labour means the children are forced to work as employees in lieu of payment of debt by the parents due to exorbitant rates of repayment of interest.

Also associated with the concept of bonded labour is the concept of urban child labour wherein the labourers are the street children who spend most of their childhood on the streets.

UNICEF has categorized child work into three categories:

1. Within the family- Children are engaged in domestic household tasks without pay.
2. within the family but outside the home- Example- agricultural labourers, domestic maids, migrant labourers etc.
3. Outside the family- Example- commercial shops in restaurants and jobs, prostitution etc.

As per Census 2011, the total child population in India in the age group (5-14) years is 259.6 million. Of these, 10.1 million (3.9% of total child population) are working, either as 'main worker' or as 'marginal worker'. In addition, more than 42.7 million children in India are out of school.

However, the good news is that the incidence of child labour has decreased in India by 2.6 million between 2001 and 2011. However, the decline was more visible in rural areas, while the number of child workers has increased in urban areas, indicating the growing demand for child workers in menial jobs. Child labour has different ramifications in both rural and urban India.

Year	Percentage of working children (5-14)			Total number of working children (5-14) (in millions)		
	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban	Total
2001	5.9	2.1	5.0	11.4	1.3	12.7
2011	4.3	2.9	3.9	8.1	2.0	10.1

*Source – Census 2001 and 2011

Distribution of working children by type of work in 2011

Area of work	Percentage	Numbers (in millions)
Cultivators	26.0	2.63
Agricultural labourers	32.9	3.33
Household industry workers	5.2	0.52
Other workers	35.8	3.62

*Source – Census 2011

Note: 'Other workers': Workers other than cultivators, agricultural labourers or workers in household industries

States with High Incidences of Child labour

Together, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Rajasthan, Maharashtra, and Madhya Pradesh constitute nearly 55% of total working children in India.

States	Percentage	Numbers (In million)
Uttar Pradesh	21.5	2.18
Bihar	10.7	1.09
Rajasthan	8.4	0.85
Maharashtra	7.2	0.73
Madhya Pradesh	6.9	0.70

*Source – Census 2011

Causes of Rising Instances of Child Labour

Over population, [illiteracy](#), [poverty](#), debt trap are some of the common causes which are instrumental in this issue.

Overburdened, debt-trapped parents fail to understand the importance of a normal childhood under the pressures of their own troubles and thus it leads to the poor emotional and mental balance of a child's brain which is not prepared to undertake rigorous field or domestic tasks.

National and Multinational companies also recruit children in garment industries for more work and less pay which is absolutely unethical.

According to UNICEF children are employed because they can be easily exploited. By considering various causes of child labour, we can make a strategy to curb or eliminate child labour.

Causes of Child Labour Child labour is caused by several factors. Some of them include:

- **The curse of poverty**

The main reason for child labour is poverty. Most of the country's population suffers from poverty. Due to poverty, parents cannot afford the studies of their children and make them earn their wages from a tender age. In fact, they are well aware of the grief of losing their loved ones to poverty many times. They send their small children to work in factories, homes and shops. They are made to work to increase the income of their poor families at the earliest. These decisions are taken only for the purpose of eking out a living for their family. But such decisions shatter children's physical and mental state as they lose their childhood at an early age.

- **Lack of educational resources**

Even after so many years of our country's independence, there are instances where children are deprived of their fundamental right to education. There are thousands of villages in our country where there are no proper facilities of education. And if there is any, it is miles away. Such administrative laxity is also responsible for child labour. The worst sufferers are the poor families for whom getting their children educated is a dream.

Sometimes the lack of affordable school for the education of poor children leaves them illiterate and helpless. Children are forced to live without studying. And sometimes such compulsions push them into the trap of child labour.

- **Social and economic backwardness**

Social and economic backwardness is also the main reason for child labour. Socially backward parents do not send their children to receive education. Consequently, their children are trapped in child labour. Due to illiteracy, many times parents are not aware of various information and schemes for child education. Lack of education, illiteracy and consequently the lack of awareness of their rights among them have encouraged child labour. Also, uneducated parents do not know about the impact of child labour on their children. The conditions of poverty and unemployment give rural families a compulsive basis for engaging children in various tasks. In fact, feudal, zamindari system and its existing remnants continue to perpetuate the problem of child labour.

- **Addiction, disease or disability**

In many families, due to addiction, disease or disability, there is no earning, and the child's wages are the sole means of family's sustenance. Population growth is also increasing unemployment, which has adverse impact on child labour prevention. So, parents, instead of sending their children to school, are willing to send them to work to increase family income.

- **Poor compliance of laws**

In modern society, laws stipulate that citizens have the right to receive good education, avail good health services and take care of their health. Every citizen has the right to play the game he enjoys, and enjoy all the means of entertainment, and when he grows, to obtain employment where he can earn well and contribute to society and nation. But in the absence of proper compliance of the laws, child labour is continuing. It can be prohibited only by strict adherence to the related laws.

- **Lure of cheap labour**

In the greed of cheap labour, some shopkeepers, companies and factory owners employ children so that they have to pay less to them and it amounts to employing cheap labour. Shopkeepers and small businessmen make children work as much as they do to the elder ones, but pay half the wages. In the case of child labour, there is less chance for theft, greed or misappropriation of money too.

With the development of globalization, privatization, and consumerist culture, the need for cheap labour and its linkage with economic needs of poor families have encouraged child labour.

- **Family tradition**

It is a shocking but a bitter truth that in our society it is very easy to give child labour the name of tradition or custom in many families. The culture and traditional family values play their role in increasing the problem of child labour at the voluntary level. Many families believe that a good life is not their destiny, and the age-old tradition of labour is the only source of their earning and livelihood.

Small businessmen also waste the lives of their children in the greediness of perpetuating their family trade with lower production costs. Some families also believe that working from childhood onwards will make their children more diligent and worldly-wise in terms of future life. They believe that early employment will give rise to their children's personal development, which will make it easier for them to plan their life ahead.

- **Discrimination between boys and girls**

We have been conditioned into believing that girls are weaker and there is no equal comparison between boys and girls. Even today, in our society, we will find many examples where girls are deprived of studies.

Considering girls weaker than boys deprives them of school and education. In labourer families, girls are found to be engaged in labour along with their parents.

CHILD LABOUR LAWS IN INDIA

Various laws have been made in our country since 1933 to control child labour:

1. Children (Pledging of labour) Act 1933.
2. Employment of child Act 1938.
3. The Bombay shop and establishment Act 1948.
4. The Indian factories Act 1948.
5. Plantation labour Act 1951.
6. The mines Act 1952.
7. Merchant shipping Act 1958
8. The apprentice Act 1961
9. The motor transport workers Act 1961
10. The atomic energy Act 1962
11. Bidi and cigar workers (condition of employment) Act 1966.
12. State shops and establishment Act
13. The child labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act 1986.
14. The juvenile justice (care and protection) of children Act, 2000.
15. Article 24 of our constitution and section 67 of the factories Act, explicitly direct that children below the age of 14 years are not allowed to work in factories.
16. Article 21A (added by the 86th amendment Act 2002) provides that state shall provide free and compulsory education to children of age group 6-14 years.
17. Article 45 provides for free and compulsory education for all children up to the age of 14 years¹.

EFFORTS BY GOVERNMENT OF INDIA TO CONTROL CHILD LABOUR

The child labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act 1986 prohibits the employment of children below the age of 14 years in 16 occupation and 65 processes that are hazardous to the children's lives and health. According to Supreme Court's direction on 10th December, 1996, recovery notice have been issued to offending employees for collection of a sum of Rs 2000 per child employed under the provision of Act. No child can be employed in hazardous occupations. Many states including Haryana have constituted the child labour rehabilitation –cum-welfare funds at district level and separate labour cells are being formed to address the issue². National child labour projects have been implemented by the central government in states from 1988 to provide non-formal education and pre-vocational skills. From 2001, Sarve shiksha Abhiyan has been launched to educate poor and employed children in all states. Ministry of women and child development has been providing non-formal education and vocational training. Establishment of Anganbadies is also a big step by the government for the welfare of children and their physical, mental and educational development.

SUGGESTIONS

1. Proper implementation of welfare schemes for children by the concerned authorities.
2. NGOs can play a very effective role in rehabilitation of child labourers.
3. Media is also an important tool to create awareness about child labour laws.

4. Major role can be played by local governments in controlling child labour.
5. In schools with free education, monetary help in the form of scholarship should be provided to the students of economically weaker families.

CONCLUSION

Child labour can be checked only when we people have little concern about the physical, mental and educational development of children around us. It is the duty of civil society not to physical help from them but provide them their childhood.

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